

Assessing rock physics and seismic characteristics of the Gassum Formation in the Stenlille aquifer gas storage – A reservoir analog for the Havnsø CO₂ storage prospect, Denmark

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ABSTRACT

The rock physics and seismic characteristics of prospective CO₂ storage sites are important inputs to assess the feasibility of seismic reservoir characterization and monitoring of the CO₂ plume. In this paper, geophysical data from the Stenlille aquifer gas storage in Denmark are used as a reservoir analog to the Gassum Formation at the Havnsø CO₂ prospect. Rock physics and pore fluid modeling of the in situ natural gas and CO₂ saturation was performed to obtain an initial understanding of the seismic-reservoir relationship and to model the seismic sensitivity for various pore fluid scenarios. Then, a 3D seismic survey at Stenlille was used as input to a Bayesian inversion for litho-fluid classification to outline the injected natural gas distributions in a probabilistic manner. Although only post-stack seismic data were available, the gas injected into the different reservoir zones of the Gassum Formation yields a low acoustic impedance signature that could be interpreted from the inversion results. The predictions were consistent with well log data, reported gas withdrawal and injection volumes and conforms with the geological structure. This implies good conditions for seismic reservoir characterization and monitoring CO₂ saturation changes in the Gassum Formation for geological settings similar to the Stenlille aquifer.

1. Introduction

In 2019 the Danish government set a political ambition to reduce national CO₂ emissions by 70% by 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050. Consequently, considerable research activities have initiated to outline best practices for secure capture and long-time geological storage of industrial emitted CO₂. Previous assessments indicated that approximately 22,000 million tons (Mt) could be stored in saline aquifers in Denmark (Anthonsen et al., 2016). The main storage potential in Denmark is within high-porosity sandstone layers of Triassic-Jurassic age, widely distributed in the subsurface. Several four-way-closure structures were identified both offshore and onshore that could form possible CO₂ storage sites. However, these preliminary calculations were based on rough screening of limited geophysical data covering Denmark, and there are currently few case studies that show how to reduce the geological risks associated with specific CO₂ storage prospects. Fig. 1a shows an overview of some geological structures identified as possible CO₂ storage prospects across Denmark from the study of Hjelm et al. (2020).

One of the most prospective CO₂ storage sites in Fig. 1 is the Havnsø anticline structure (Anthonsen et al., 2014; Larsen et al., 2007), situated close to the small seaport of Havnsø (55.75° North, 11.3° East) in Sjælland, see Fig. 1(b). The structure covers approximately 160 km² of the Gassum sandstone formation buried at approximately 1500 m depth. One-third and two-thirds of the structure is situated offshore and onshore, respectively, with an estimated storage capacity between 200–400 Mt of CO₂. An 80% probability is estimated for the geological feasibility of CO₂ storage in the Gassum Formation at Havnsø (Hjelm et al., 2020). The structure is particularly interesting due to the proximity of two large CO₂ emission sources; a coal fired power plant and a refinery located close to Kalundborg. In addition, the Danish capital Copenhagen lies only 85 km away with supplementary CO₂ point sources. Moreover, the estimated costs for transporting and injecting CO₂ are lower for onshore compared to offshore storage sites. The Havnsø structure is covered by old, low quality 2D seismic lines, and no wells have yet been drilled to evaluate the geological model and reservoir quality of the Gassum Formation.

The lack of modern remote geophysical data and nearby wells is a

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particular problem for geological site selection and reservoir characterization in Denmark. Previous assessments of the Havnsø CO₂ prospect are mainly based on extrapolating data from the Stenlille saline aquifer gas storage facility, located approximately 30 km southeast of the Havnsø structure (Fig. 1c). At Stenlille, natural gas has been injected into and stored in the Gassum sandstone reservoir since 1989, serving as a subsurface buffer for the annual supply and demand chain of natural gas. The reservoir occurs within a domal closure and is overlain by seal-forming mudstones of the Fjerritslev Formation. The geological setting at Stenlille is assumed to represent a good analog to the Havnsø structure since similar lithologies and burial depths for the Gassum Formation are expected. The average porosity (25%) and net-to-gross (0.7) in the Gassum sandstone reservoir at Stenlille represent good conditions for geological CO₂ storage.

The Stenlille aquifer gas storage structure was initially identified from 2D seismic lines. A 3D seismic survey was acquired later in 1997, and there are currently twenty wells used for injection, withdrawal and monitoring of gas at the Stenlille storage facility. In general, the seismic reflection method is considered the best remote sensing tool for creating high-resolution subsurface images that can be interpreted in terms of reservoir quality and pore fluid content. Monitoring the spatial distribution and saturation of fluids, such as CO₂ and natural gas, are also demonstrated with the use of repeated seismic measurements (Arts et al., 2003; Chadwick et al., 2005; Glubokovskikh et al., 2016; Hansen et al., 2011). The dataset at Stenlille is the most comprehensive onshore dataset in Denmark, and has led to a good local understanding of the geological and petrophysical properties of the Gassum sandstone reservoir and the Fjerritslev cap-rock (e.g. Kristensen et al., 2016; Laier and Øbro, 2009; Weibel et al., 2017). However, the dataset has several limitations – it contains substantial noise, lacks pre-stack seismic gathers

and the wells contain sporadic log data content – which constrain methods for quantitative interpretations (Chadwick et al., 2010; Ghosh et al., 2015; Queißer and Singh, 2013). Despite the usefulness of the Stenlille 3D dataset for studying natural gas storage, CO₂ storage and geothermal resources in Denmark, there is only the study of Trappe et al. (2002) that has reported using it by demonstrating a neural network approach to map the gas column height in one of the Gassum reservoir zones. Furthermore, Hall et al. (2010) present some rock physics modeling of the Gassum Formation based on Stenlille well log data. More recently, Pasquinelli et al. (2020) investigated the feasibility of using the Gassum Formation in the Stenlille structure for heat storage by developing a 3D heat storage model from 2D seismic data and well logs. In addition, the Gassum sandstone reservoir has been characterized in terms of porosity, lithology and permeability for geothermal purposes based on 2D seismic pre-stack and well log data located close to Hillerød in the northeastern part of Denmark (Bredesen et al., 2018; 2020; Chopra et al., 2021; Dalgaard et al., 2019; Feng et al., 2020).

This paper presents a rock physics and seismic assessment using available well log and post-stack 3D seismic data covering the Stenlille aquifer. The work is an integrated part of a larger research project aiming at investigation of technical barriers for safe and environmentally friendly permanent CO₂ storage in Denmark. The main objectives of this study are:

1. Perform rock physics modeling and fluid substitution of the seismic response for various fluid scenarios, including CO₂, at the Stenlille aquifer.
2. Perform a Bayesian seismic inversion for litho-fluid classification to outline the spatial distribution of injected natural gas at the time of the seismic survey.

Fig. 1. Location maps showing (a) identified structures in the Danish area relevant for CO₂ storage within different formations (modified from Hjelm et al. (2020)), (b) Sjælland with the Havnsø prospect outlined, and (c) zoom in at the Stenlille area with well positions and the 3D seismic survey. Many wells have approximately the same surface position and plot on top of each other. Courtesy of Google Maps.

In the following sections, the key geological settings and reservoir targets are introduced. Rock physics analysis, fluid replacement and seismic modeling based on well log data are presented. Finally, the classification of a gas saturated sandstone from a Bayesian seismic post-stack inversion is presented, focusing on gas distribution within the main reservoir zones used for gas storage.

2. Overview of geology and gas storage at Stenlille

Denmark is characterized by a thick sedimentary package of Late Palaeozoic Cenozoic age. These units are up to 9 km thick in the Danish Basin and bounded to the north by the Fennoscandian Border Zone characterized by a relatively thin succession of Triassic, Jurassic and Early Cretaceous age. To the south, the Danish Basin is bound by the northwest-southeast striking basement high, the Ringkøbing-Fyn High. The sedimentary cover on this structural high is relatively thin (12 km) and characterized by the absence of Upper Permian sediments, thin Triassic and thin or absent Jurassic sediments. The North German Basin is situated south of the basement high with sediment thickness comparable to the Danish Basin (Frederiksen et al., 2001; Larsen et al., 2007; Michelsen et al., 2003).

Initially, five lithostratigraphic formations were considered for potential CO₂ storage in the deep saline aquifers in Denmark. These are the Triassic Bunter Sandstone and Skagerrak Formations, Upper Triassic-Lower Jurassic Gassum Formation, Middle Jurassic Haldager Sand Formation and Upper Jurassic-Lower Cretaceous Frederikshavn Formation. The Gassum Formation is considered to have the most promising reservoir properties with respect to the burial depth and shows good thickness and continuity between 100 and 150 m throughout most of Denmark. The Gassum Formation consists of fine- to medium-grained, locally coarse-grained sandstones interbedded with claystones and locally thin coal layers. The porosity (18-27%, maximum 36%) and permeability (up to 2000 mD) of the sandstones are known from a number of wells (Kristensen et al., 2016; Larsen et al., 2007). The sediments were deposited under repeated sea-level fluctuations at a time where the majority of the Danish depositional area was a shallow sea to which rivers transported large quantities of sand eroded mainly from the Fennoscandian basement region. A large part of the sandstones in the Gassum Formation represent shoreface deposits, but significant amounts of sandstones representing deposition in rivers and estuaries are also present. This is especially the case for the lower part of the formation where high-order relative sea level falls were more pronounced, and led to the progradation of rivers and estuaries into the central part of the Danish Basin thereby forming laterally continuous sheets of sandstones separated by mudstone intervals representing deposition either in offshore, lagoonal, or lacustrine environments (Michelsen et al., 2003). The Gassum Formation is already exploited as a natural gas storage reservoir at Stenlille and as a geothermal reservoir at Thisted and Sønderborg.

At the Stenlille facility, the natural gas is stored in an anticline structure defined by six sandstone reservoir zones in the Gassum Formation. The structure formed as a result of salt movements in the Zechstein Formation approximately 2800 m below the surface. The primary sealing unit for the Gassum Sandstone Formation is the Lower Jurassic Fjerritslev Formation, which constitutes approximately 300 m of marine claystone and mudstone (Laiet and Øbro, 2009). The Gassum Sandstone reservoir is approximately 140 m thick, but only the upper 40 m is used for storage in order to prevent gas migration through the spill-point. The upper 40 m are divided into various gas storage zones segregated by thin shale beds (Fig. 2a). The estimated total gas storage volume is 3 billion Nm^{3*} within the four-way closure, covering an area

of approximately 14 km².

Today, there are 14 operational gas injection and production wells and six observation wells located at the fringes of the anticline structure, for monitoring pressure in the aquifer around the gas reservoir and in the caprock (Fig. 1). Gas is stored in zones 1–5 only, which operate as two separate units: (i) zones 1–3 operate as one integrated unit from four injection wells and (ii) zone 5 operates from ten injection wells. Fig. 2(b) shows the total gas volumes between 1980 and 2005 including the collection of the 3D seismic survey and the drilling of various wells. At the time of the seismic survey in 1997, approximately 510 and 340 million Nm³ of natural gas were injected into zones 1–3 and zone 5, respectively. Gas injections were predominantly via Stenlille-2, 7, 9 and 11 for zones 1–3 and via Stenlille-8, 14, 16 and 18 for zone 5.

Figure 3 shows a well-tied sequence stratigraphic subdivision of the Gassum Formation between Stenlille-1 and Stenlille-19, with depositional environments and reservoir zonation. The sequence stratigraphic subdivision is mainly based on interpretation of sedimentological core descriptions (Hovikoski and Pedersen, 2020), vertical gamma-ray log motifs and biostratigraphic analysis (Vosgerau et al., 2020). A core photo from Stenlille-19 shows some facies variations in the upper part of zone 6 sand. The reservoir zones are primarily defined for reservoir management purposes such that gas injection and withdrawal are operated in a productive and safe manner.

3. Data coverage

Almost all wells contain density logs and petrophysical logs (i.e. porosity, shale volume and water saturation), 12 wells additionally include a compressional sonic log and 2 wells include a shear sonic log covering the Gassum Formation interval. The complete set of these logs is important to study the relationships between seismic (or elastic) properties and reservoir (or petrophysical) properties (Dvorkin et al., 2014; Waters and Kemper, 2014).

A 3D seismic survey covering approximately 56.4 km² was collected in 1997. The aim was to map distributions of the various reservoir zones, evaluate reservoir quality and gas saturation from amplitude vs. offset (AVO) analysis, identify any secondary structural heights, faults that may limit the gas filling, and the spill-point of the anticline structure. However, seismic data in a pre-stack format was unavailable for this study, which could be used as input to quantitative interpretation techniques, such as AVO analysis (Dvorkin et al., 2014; Simm et al., 2014) and pre-stack inversion (Bredesen et al., 2020; Buland et al., 2008; Grana et al., 2017). Hence, this study is restricted to the available 3D post-stack seismic volume only. Fig. 4 displays a seismic profile along an arbitrary line extracted from the 3D seismic volume with the gamma ray logs for the intersecting wells overlaid. Five interpreted horizons overlay the seismic data: Base Chalk, Near Top Fjerritslev, Intra Fjerritslev (sandstone layer), Upper target and Base target. The Gassum reservoir is bounded by the Upper target and Base target horizons, where decreasing gamma ray curves correlate to presence of sandstones with low clay content. Notice that a clear drop in the gamma ray curves do not align with a laterally continuous and distinctive reflection event for the top of the Gassum target interval. In fact, picking a laterally continuous and robust reflection event for the upper Gassum sandstone unit with a good well tie tends to be challenging, and the Upper target horizon is therefore used as an approximation. This might partly be explained by that the top of the Gassum Formation represents a bumpy rather than smooth marine transgression boundary, where deep marine sediments (clay and silt) have flooded a sandy shallow marine environment composed of lagoons and island barriers. Likewise, the Base target horizon selected tends to sit deeper than the corresponding sequence stratigraphic boundaries observed in the wells. Nevertheless, for the inversion objectives of this study, these horizons were primarily selected to represent upper and lower bounds for the seismic inversion window to capture the whole Gassum reservoir target.

* Nm³: Normal cubic meter, the volume of natural gas occupying the volume of one cubic meter under dry conditions at 0 °C temperature and 1.01325 bar of pressure

Fig. 2. (a) Illustrative cross section (SWNE) of the Stenlille natural gas underground storage showing the various reservoir zones. Well locations are indicated at the top of the figure. Extracted from [Laiet and Øbro \(2009\)](#). (b) Natural gas volumes at the Stenlille aquifer gas storage facility between 1980 and 2005 and times of data acquisition for the 3D seismic and wells.

Fig. 3. Left: Stenlille-1 and Stenlille-19 wells with gamma-ray log (GR) and sonic log (DT), well-tied sequence stratigraphic surfaces (red lines), overall depositional environments in Stenlille-19 ([Hovikoski and Pedersen, 2020](#)) and reservoir zonation. Yellow and brown color infills indicate intervals dominated by sandstone and mudstone, respectively. Modified from [Vosgerau et al. \(2020\)](#). Right: core photo from Stenlille-19 showing some facies variations in the upper part of zone 6 sand (from [Hovikoski and Pedersen \(2020\)](#)). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

To achieve a better 3D sense, [Fig. 5](#) shows the Upper target horizon that approximates the upper Gassum sandstone unit in map-view with the arbitrary line ([Fig. 4](#)) indicated in dashed white. The Stenlille anticline structure is outlined by the red color indicating shallower depths. The Gassum reservoir apex corresponds to a depth of approximately

1500 m below ground level.

4. Rock physics and fluid substitution analysis

To better understand how the reservoir properties in the Gassum

Fig. 4. An arbitrary line extracted from the seismic volume intersecting seven wells with the corresponding gamma ray logs overlaid. The Gassum reservoir target is bounded by the Upper target and Base target horizons. TWT: Two-Way-Time.

Fig. 5. Horizon surface from the Upper target as a colored surface and isoline contours in mapview with the location of wells along the white arbitrary line in Fig. 4.

sandstone affect the seismic characteristics, rock physics analysis was performed based on well log data (e.g. Caspari et al., 2015; Grana et al., 2017; Hao et al., 2016). For low-offset post-stack seismic data, seismic reflections are primarily governed by the contrasts in acoustic impedance (AI) across rock interfaces (Shuey, 1985). Fig. 6 shows various distributions of AI log data grouped by wells and by different depth intervals. The cap-rock interval refers to the lowermost 50 m of the Fjerritslev Formation above the Gassum Formation in this figure. The stacked AI distributions in Fig. 6 shows that the older Stenlille wells (i.e. Stenlille-1, 2, 3, etc.) exhibit higher AI than the later wells because gas was not yet injected into these first exploration and appraisal wells (Fig. 2b). The AI distributions grouped into different depth intervals show higher AI in Fjerritslev than in the Gassum Formation. However, the distributions exhibit high variance due to the heterogeneities in the Gassum and Fjerritslev intervals composed of alternating shale and

sandstone layers with varying AI.

4.1. Rock physics cross-plot analysis

To make our rock physics analysis as relevant as possible for the seismic data, we focus on a subset of wells that was drilled around the same time as the seismic was collected in 1997 and when gas was injected into both zones 1–3 and zone 5 (Fig. 2b). Fig. 7 shows a matrix of cross-plots between AI and different reservoir and pore fluid properties for the various reservoir zones from Stenlille-17, 18 and 19. The diagonal cross-plots show a kernel density estimate (Silverman, 2018) for each property, whereas the off-diagonal scatter-plots show the relationships between two given properties. These plots can be used to investigate the relationships between the various properties. For example, higher porosity and lower water saturation yield lower AI, porosity and shale volume correlates linearly, and the more shaly zones (Fig. 3) exhibit higher AI.

Complete rock physics analysis require shear sonic logs to derive the independent elastic properties. Well Stenlille-19 includes a suite of logs measured in 2001 including shear sonic, and is therefore used as a reference well as it also contains checkshot data useful for a seismic-well tie. Fig. 8 shows, left-to-right, the porosity and fluid saturations, shale volume, AI and the P-to-S velocity ratio logs from Stenlille-19 covering the Gassum Formation. The upper part of the Gassum Formation is characterized by more interchanging shale beds (zone 1–4), whereas zone 5 and 6 are composed of thicker units of clean sandstones with an average porosity of approximately 27%. An 11 m gas column with approximately 70% gas saturation is located in the top of the zone 5 sandstone. A 5–15% gas saturation in the sandstone zones above are observed as well.

A cross-plot of acoustic impedance (AI) vs. the P-to-S velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) from Stenlille-19 provides an initial impression of the seismic properties of the Gassum sandstone reservoir (Fig. 9). The data are colored according to porosity, shale volume and water saturation to reveal any seismic-reservoir relationships. The porosity is negatively correlated with AI (also see Fig. 6), whereas increasing volume of shale exhibits higher V_p/V_s and AI, and higher gas saturations yield a decrease in V_p/V_s and AI. These results indicate that seismic properties are sensitive to variations in reservoir properties and pore fluid content. Hence, if AI and V_p/V_s parameters could be derived from seismic data with sufficient resolution, they could be used to obtain quantitative

Fig. 6. Distributions of AI data grouped by: (a) all wells within the Gassum Formation interval, AI grouped by different depth intervals (b) for all wells and (c) Stenlille-19 data. Cap-rock refers to the 50 m interval lying above the Gassum Formation. Dashed vertical lines represent the mean value of the distributions.

Fig. 7. Matrix of cross-plots of various seismic and reservoir properties: acoustic impedance, porosity, shale volume and water saturation from Stenlille-17, 18 and 19. The data are colored according to reservoir zonation.

interpretations of the reservoir properties. However, as only post-stack seismic data are available, we can only invert for AI and thereby interpret reservoir changes projected onto the x-axis in Fig. 9. It is therefore worth noticing that the gas separates from the water saturated sandstones along the x-axis, but at the same time, it is more challenging to distinguish between pore fluid saturations and porosity variations without additional V_p/V_s data. In other words, we are dealing with a more non-unique and undetermined inverse problem with only AI data

available.

4.2. Rock physics model calibration

To obtain better quantitative control of how reservoir variations are related to elastic and seismic properties, a rock physics model for the Gassum Formation was calibrated. In Bredesen et al. (2018, 2020), a constant cement model (Avseth et al., 2010) was used to describe well

Fig. 8. Logs from Stenlille-19, from left-to-right: porosity, shale volume, acoustic impedance and the P-to-S velocity ratio (V_p/V_s). Reservoir zonation is shown by the colored column to the right. Note that Zones 2a and 2b are considered equal in Stenlille-19.

Fig. 9. Cross-plot of acoustic impedance versus P-to-S velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) data from Stenlille-19 for the Gassum sandstone reservoir color-coded with (a) porosity, (b) shale volume, and (c) water saturation.

log data from the Copenhagen area to characterize the Gassum Formation in a geothermal exploration study. The constant cement model is designed for sandstones at burial depths where higher temperature and pressure initiate a chemical reaction resulting in cement precipitation within the pore space. The model then assumes that further porosity reduction is caused by increasing noncontact pore-filling material from

sorting effects or cement precipitation (Avseth et al., 2010) as illustrated in Fig. 10. A more detailed description of the rock physics modeling is presented in the attached supplementary material.

Fig. 11 (a) shows a porosity vs. compressional modulus cross-plot with the constant cement model for a brine-filled sandstone plotted on top of Stenlille-19 data for various shale volumes up to 40%. The constituent properties used in the rock physics modeling are shown in Table 1. The data were fluid substituted to 100% brine using the Gassmann fluid substitution (Gassmann, 1951) to eliminate pore fluid effects. The model describes the elastic properties of the Gassum sandstone reservoir reasonably well, including sections with higher shale content. In Fig. 11(b) the so-called rock physics templates (RPT) (Ødegaard and Avseth, 2004) are plotted on top of the AI vs. V_p/V_s data equivalent to Fig. 9(c) (be aware of different axis scaling in the two figures). The RPTs represent a 100% quartz sandstone and show a good consistency between the modeled and observed porosities and brine saturations for the clean sandstone data.

The estimation of the effective fluid bulk modulus (i.e. fluid incompressibility) that goes into the Gassmann equation depends on how the various fluids are mixed (or distributed) (Mavko et al., 2009), as shown

Fig. 10. Conceptual illustration of the rock physics constant cement model (Avseth et al., 2010).

Fig. 11. Rock physics modeling of Stenlille-19 data: (a) Porosity versus compressional modulus (or P-wave modulus) for varying shale volumes (data represents 100% water), (b) rock physics templates for a 100% quartz sandstone with varying porosity and water saturation plotted on top of acoustic impedance vs. V_p / V_s data, and (c) different models to mix water with gas shown for varying water saturation versus the effective bulk modulus of the fluid.

Table 1

Constituent properties used in rock physics modeling. The natural gas and brine properties are derived from the rock physics calibration procedure (Fig. 12). The CH₄ properties were calculated from empirical relations given in Batzle and Wang (1992).

Constituent	Bulk moduli [GPa]	Shear moduli [GPa]	Density [kg/m ³]
Quartz	37	44	2650
Clay	16	6	2600
Water/Brine	3.5	-	980
In situ gas	0.13	-	450
CO ₂	0.096	-	699
CH ₄	0.031	-	109
80%CO ₂ /20% CH ₄	0.067	-	580

in Fig. 11c) with some various mixing models. The upper (red) and lower (blue) bounds represent the Wood (1955) (uniform saturation) and Voigt (1928) (patchy saturation) models, respectively. The Brie et al. (1995) empirical fluid mixing model plots in between the bounds for

various exponential factors e . These mixing models address different characteristic length scale of saturation heterogeneities compared with the measurement frequency, which determines whether there is sufficient time for pore fluid pressure gradient equilibrium across different pores (Avseth et al., 2005; Caspari et al., 2015). For example, for low frequency measurements, the pore fluid pressure have enough time to equilibrate across individual pores, causing friction between the pore fluids and solid grains through pore throats, which leads to absorption of wave energy and thereby lower wave velocities. In such cases, a softer mixing model in Fig. 11(c) would be more appropriate to apply. Finding the most appropriate mixing models and constituent properties for a specific dataset is in practice a calibration procedure. Fig. 12 shows how porosity, shale volume and water saturation logs from Stenlille-19 are used as input into the rock physics model to estimate the density, P-velocity and S-velocity for uniform and patchy fluid saturation models. The models differ in the P-velocity where the patchy model apparently yields a better match to the data samples where $S_w \neq 1$. Notice how the uniform model yields a considerable decrease in P-velocity even for small water saturation reductions, which is reflected by the non-linear relationship of the Wood fluid mixing model shown in

Fig. 12. Stenlille-19 logs of shale volume (V_{sh}), water saturation (S_w) and porosity (to the left) used as input to a rock physics model to estimate density, P-velocity and S-velocity using the Wood (uniform) and patchy fluid saturation models. The blue shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval of the patchy fluid saturation model. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11(c). Furthermore, the applied rock physics model tends to overestimate the S-velocities as a consequence of assuming uniform grain contacts, leading to erroneously high effective tangential shear stiffness (Bachrach and Avseth, 2008; Dvorkin and Nur, 1996). However, on a larger scale, such as the seismic scale, the model predicts the effective rock physics properties reasonably well.

4.3. Fluid replacement modeling

To investigate the seismic response for different fluid scenarios in the Stenlille aquifer, the fluid substitution recipe of Gassmann (1951) was used. We consider three different scenarios: (1) in situ conditions, (2) replacing the natural gas with a 80%CO₂/20%CH₄ mixture (Caspari et al., 2015), and (3) 100% water saturation. For scenario (2), the bulk modulus and density of the CO₂ and CH₄ were estimated individually as functions of the temperature and pressure conditions measured in the Gassum Formation in Stenlille-19. For the CO₂ properties, Fig. 13 shows the bulk modulus and density as function of temperature and pressure based on the equation of state presented by Span and Wagner (1996). The red crosses mark a temperature of 52 °C and a formation pressure of 16 MPa as measured in Stenlille-19, indicating normal hydrostatic pressure conditions. This corresponds to a bulk modulus and density of 0.096 GPa and 699 kg/m³, respectively (Table 1). Notice the abrupt increase in density and bulk modulus at the lower pressure regime, corresponding to a gas–liquid transition. A more gradual change in the acoustic properties are seen for the gas-supercritical phase (Njiekak et al., 2013). The CH₄ properties were estimated using the empirical relations of Batzle and Wang (1992) based on the same temperature and pore pressure and a gas gravity of 0.56 (ratio of gas density to air density at 15.6 °C and atmospheric pressure) (Mavko et al., 2009). Notice in Table 1 that the CH₄ bulk moduli and density is much smaller than the gas properties used in the rock physics model calibration that gave the best density fit (Fig. 12). This may indicate that the natural gas injected into the Stenlille aquifer is a mixture of methane and some heavier gas compounds, or that the density log is inaccurate. Finally, the CO₂ and CH₄ are intimately mixed 80%/20% at the finest scale into an effective fluid using Wood's mixing model (Caspari et al., 2015).

After calculating the acoustic properties for a 80%CO₂/20%CH₄ mixture, the seismic response for various fluid scenarios are evaluated from fluid replacement modeling. Fig. 14 shows, from left to right, porosity, water saturation, density, P-velocity, and S-velocity, and synthetic seismic traces for various fluid scenarios. To the right, a statistical seismic wavelet and the frequency spectrum of the 3D Stenlille seismic data is shown (more details on the wavelet extraction follows later). For

the logs, a Gassmann fluid substitution (Gassmann, 1951) was applied to predict two possible fluid scenarios: (1) replacing the in situ natural gas saturation with a 80%CO₂/20%CH₄ mixture, and (2) 100% brine. For each depth sample the porosity, shale volume and brine saturation logs are used as input to calculate the effective elastic properties of the solid constituents (i.e. the grains) using a lower Hashin-Shtrikman-Walpole bound (Walpole, 1966a; 1966b). The synthetic seismic traces are generated by convolving the statistical wavelet with the reflectivity series from the acoustic impedance logs (Bianco, 2014), with a trough signal representing an increase in AI (i.e. reverse polarity). The seismic data traces are extracted along the Stenlille-19 well path and ties reasonably well to the in situ synthetic seismic, with a maximum correlation coefficient that exceeds 0.8 within the Gassum interval. In the injected gas column in the upper part of zone 5 sandstone, the density and velocities for the 100% brine saturation scenario deviates significantly from the in situ natural gas and 80%CO₂/20%CH₄ scenarios. This indicates that the Gassum sandstones are seismically sensitive to the different modeled pore fluids, as also predicted by our calibrated rock physics model (Fig. 11). Note how substituting 100% water decreases the peak response at the top of Zone 5 due to reduced acoustic impedance contrast. This plot indicates that the natural gas storage at Stenlille represents a good case analog for studying how variable CO₂ saturation affects the seismic response in the Gassum Formation with a similar lithology and burial depth.

5. Bayesian seismic inversion for litho-fluid classification

In seismic inversion, we attempt to go from relative interface properties (e.g. seismic amplitude, traveltimes, reflection coefficient) to absolute layer properties (e.g. acoustic impedance, density, porosity). In this study, the Bayesian inversion method described by Buland et al. (2008) and Kolbjørnsen et al. (2020, 2016) was adopted, using the Stenlille post-stack 3D cube as input. In general, this type of seismic inversion can be useful for boosting reservoir resolution, incorporating geological information and classifying the seismic data into litho-fluid classes (LFC) in a probabilistic manner. Fig. 15 shows a conceptual illustration of the inversion approach. At the top of the figure, the relationships between three different parameter domains are shown: LFCs (e.g. water sand, gas sand and shale), elastic properties (e.g. velocity, impedance and density) and seismic data (e.g. amplitude, traveltimes and frequency). Each of the parameter domains are represented by an illustration below. In the lower left, Markov chains (de Figueiredo et al., 2019; Mukerji et al., 2001) generate a set of possible vertical configurations of LFCs illustrated by various stacked blocks. Each LFC 'block'

Fig. 13. The acoustic properties of CO₂ as a function of temperature and pressure: (a) density and (b) bulk modulus (Span and Wagner, 1996). The red "x" represents the normal temperature and pressure conditions in the Gassum reservoir as measured in Stenlille-19. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 14. Fluid replacement and synthetic seismic modeling for different fluid scenarios tied to Stenlille-19. TWT: Two-Way-Time.

corresponds to the seismic sampling, which is 2 ms in this study. In the middle, the elastic properties of the LFCs are extracted from well-log data or calculated from a rock physics model (Avseth et al., 2005). Then, the reflection coefficients are calculated from the elastic properties (only the acoustic impedance in this study) and convolved with a wavelet to create synthetic seismic, as illustrated to the right. The inversion experiments with a range of LFC configurations (for example, 176 facies combinations were tested in this study) by comparing their synthetic seismic response with the real seismic post-stack data trace-by-trace (Buland et al., 2008). If a good fit is achieved between the synthetic and data, that specific LFC configuration is assigned a high probability value.

The inversion requires a certain setup of preconditioned data extracted from the seismic and well log data before execution, such as interpreted horizons, a wavelet and the elastic properties of specific LFCs. Fig. 16 shows the schematic workflow used in this study containing the main processes and inputs to the Bayesian LFC classification, and the primary (posterior LFC probabilities) and secondary (prior LFC probabilities, elastic properties and synthetic seismic) outputs. In the following, a description of some of the key processes are presented, interspersed with examples, before using the inversion results to map the spatial distributions of the injected natural gas in the Stenlille aquifer.

5.1. Preconditioning of seismic data

The initial processing sequence of the available 3D seismic cube from Stenlille contains a 3D Kirchhoff dip moveout correction and pre-stack time migration (PSTM) for improved resolution and signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio. The final mute was shaped to preserve all events below 800 ms, corresponding roughly to the Base Chalk interface (Fig. 4). For the inversion, a Gaussian smoothing filter and a 3D edge preserving smoothing filter were added to improve the signal-to-noise ratio and lateral continuity of reflection events. Care was taken to preserve lateral amplitude variations for the reflection events to avoid the inversion confounding processing effects with possible variations in the LFCs.

5.2. Well-to-seismic tie

Figure 17 illustrates the correlation of acoustic impedance logs, gamma ray, synthetic and real seismic traces along the Stenlille-19 well path. A statistical wavelet (shown at the bottom) was estimated within a

525 ms window around the Gassum Formation. The wavelet extraction window was designed to be long enough to capture the lowest frequency signals, but to also avoid including strong events outside our zone of interest, such as the Base Chalk event. A well-to-seismic tie was performed for the wells containing an acoustic impedance log, where a varying bulk time shift was applied to improve the correlation. This action is typically needed to compensate for the seismic dispersion phenomena (Winkler, 1986) and the missing gap of shallow log data from ground level. In Stenlille-19, a reasonably strong correlation is noticed within the Gassum interval, whereas the correlation obtained within the Fjerritslev interval is lower. The key horizons bounding our Gassum target interval, namely Upper target and Base target, shows some deviation to the Top and Base Gassum formation tops along the Stenlille-19 well path (purple dots). In general, it was difficult to pick and track reflection events corresponding to the top and base Gassum over the whole 3D seismic volume. For the purpose of the seismic inversion, horizons that exhibit lateral consistency and bounds the target interval over the whole 3D seismic volume were picked, despite that the horizons may not exactly align with the sequence boundaries of the Gassum Formation. Nevertheless, this misalignment was honoured by assigning uncertainties onto the various horizons in the inversion as demonstrated in the following content.

5.3. Litho-fluid class definition

The objective of the post-stack seismic inversion is to investigate whether it is possible to distinguish different LFCs with separable P-impedances, the product of P-velocity and density. This is because the P-impedance contrast between different LFCs governs the reflection amplitudes in the post-stack data. In this study, the focus is to investigate whether the inversion can distinguish low P-impedance gas saturated sandstones from the water saturated sandstones and shaly beds. If this happens to be the case, it implies that the seismic post-stack resolves the injected gas into the Stenlille aquifer and, therefore, would be equally feasible for mapping a growing CO₂ plume (Fig. 14). The well logs from Stenlille-19 were used to generate the LFCs, as it is not only logged deeper but carries more curves and is consistent with the other wells, such as Stenlille-17 and 18 (Fig. 6) drilled close to the time of the seismic survey.

Fig. 18 shows the porosity and water saturation, shale volume and P-impedance logs from Stenlille-19, with the colored intervals used for the LFC definitions plotted on top. The main intervals of interest are the low

Fig. 15. Conceptual illustration of the seismic inversion approach. Top: relationships between the different domains of discrete litho-fluid classes (LFC) f , the elastic properties m , and the seismic data d (from Kolbjørnsen et al. (2020)). Bottom: vertical configuration of different LFCs (left), rock physics cross-plot of elastic properties for the different LFCs (middle), and a synthetic seismic trace from convolving the elastic properties (only the acoustic impedance in this study) with a given wavelet (right).

Fig. 16. Schematic workflow diagram for the Bayesian seismic inversion for classification of different litho-fluid classes (LFCs). PSTM: Pre-Stack Time Migration.

Fig. 17. Correlation of the Stenlille-19 well logs with the seismic data. A reasonably good correlation coefficient between 0.6 and 0.8 was obtained between the synthetic trace (generated with the wavelet shown below) and the seismic trace along the Stenlille-19 well path within the Gassum interval. Purple dots corresponds to formation tops in Stenlille-19.

P-impedance gas sandstone (extracted from the 11 m gas column in the upper zone 5), the water sandstones in zone 5 and 6, high P-impedance shales (extracted from zone 6 shale layer), and the more heterogeneous

upper part of the Gassum (zones 1–4) with more varying P-impedances. In addition, intervals for the lower Fjerritslev and upper Vinding intervals were defined to represent overburden and underburden LFCs,

Fig. 18. Definition of litho-fluid classes (LFCs) based on P-velocity and density data extracted from different colored intervals specified in the Stenlille-19 well.

respectively. Notice that the intervals merge some of the previous reservoir zones with similar P-impedances into a single litho-fluid class, e.g. water sandstones in zone 5 and 6. This simplification is done to reduce the number of LFCs going into the inversion, thereby reducing the non-uniqueness of the problem and boosting inversion calculation speed. For each interval, statistical mean values, standard deviations and correlations between the P-velocity and density are extracted for each LFC and used to calculate Gaussian distributions and probability density functions (PDFs), as illustrated by the P-velocity vs. density cross-plots to the right in Fig. 18. The PDFs represent the rock physics likelihood models used to calculate the posterior probabilities for each LFC (Fig. 15) (Kolbjørnsen et al., 2020). The cross-plots also provide hints as to which LFC could be expected to be seismically distinguished

by looking at the P-velocity and density separations. The more the PDFs overlap, the more difficult it is for the inversion to discriminate them from one another.

5.4. Inversion setup and QC

Figure 19 shows inversion QC plots along Stenlille-19 well path, showing left-to-right, LFC probabilities from the prior and posterior, reservoir zonation (Fig. 8), input seismic data, inverted seismic (i.e. synthetic), residuals and inverted acoustic impedance (red curve) plotted on top of the well log data (black curve). The prior probabilities are specified such that the Fjerritslev and Vinding LFCs represents the overburden and underburden of the Gassum interval, respectively.

Fig. 19. Inversion results for Gassum interval along Stenlille-19. From left-to-right, LFC probabilities from the prior and posterior, reservoir zonation in Stenlille-19, input seismic data along the well path, inverted seismic (i.e. synthetic), residuals and derived acoustic impedance (red curve) plotted on top of the well log data (black curve). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Within the Gassum interval, the prior probability of the remaining LFCs are equalized, and a constant 10% prior probability is also assigned to an "Undefined" LFC, in case none of the other LFCs match the seismic data. Smooth transition boundaries in the prior model at the Upper target horizon (blue) and Base target horizon (cyan) are a result of assigning ± 15 ms uncertainty to the horizons, as illustrated by the shaded intervals around the horizons. The posterior probabilities represent the main output of the inversion, where we can observe how the seismic data influence the inversion results by comparing it with the prior probabilities. If the seismic data do not contain any useful information for the inversion, the inversion will lean on the prior probabilities such that posterior probabilities \approx prior probabilities. In this case, the inversion suggests some high probability anomalies for the gas sandstone and zone 6 shale LFCs that are in alignment with some of the zones these are expected to occur. High probability for zone 6 shale is predicted in zone 4, zone 5 clay and zone 6 clay, whereas gas sandstone has high-probability within zone 2 and 3, top of Zone 5 and Zone 6. These predictions are all reasonable, except for the false gas anomaly in Zone 6 as this unit is not used for gas storage. Moreover, the Stenlille-19 water saturation log does not show any high-gas volumes in Zone 3 (Fig. 8), but that can partly be due to different net gas volumes in zone 2 and 3 between the Stenlille-19 log measurements and the 3D seismic survey (Fig. 2b).

The inversion seems to favor the gas sandstone LFC in places where a strong peak is present in the seismic (decrease in AI). Likewise, the zone 6 shale LFC aligns with trough events (increase in AI). The error (or difference) between the input and inverted seismic traces are seen on the residuals. Relatively small errors imply accurate inversion results. Finally, the inverted AI calculated from a weighted mean based on the LFCs posterior probability distributions is shown. The inverted AI is a secondary (or derived) inversion product for QC and parameter tuning. The inverted AI follows the dynamics of the AI log reasonably well, but there are some over and underpredictions in the upper part of the Gassum interval. But then again, this may be due to different net gas volumes present when the Stenlille-19 logs and the seismic data were recorded.

5.5. Mapping gas distributions in the Stenlille aquifer

For the seismic mapping of the natural gas storage distribution, we could expect to see the fluid response for the net volumes present at the time of the seismic survey during autumn 1997 (Fig. 2b). Fig. 20 shows a posterior probability section of the gas sandstone LFC covering the Gassum interval along an arbitrary line, intersecting Stenlille-1, 17, 18 and 4. In Stenlille-1 and 4, shale volume logs are projected on top of the probability section because the wells were drilled respectively in 1980

and 1988 prior to the startup of gas injection. A laterally consistent high-probability gas anomaly is prominent that aligns with the zone 3 gas saturations in Stenlille-17 and 18. The inversion also captures some more shallow gas anomalies representing zone 1 and 2, and some deeper discontinuous anomalies representing zone 5. Even though a good match is obtained between the inversion and water saturation logs, it should be noted that this comparison is not 1:1 because the net gas volumes are annually cyclic (Fig. 2b). Typically, the gas is depleted during cold winter months, whereas gas accumulates in the rest of the year to a net gain. At the time of the seismic survey during the autumn of 1997, there was no simultaneous well log measurements performed, and the saturation logs do therefore not necessarily represent the exact same gas volumes as during the seismic survey. The main gas columns (around 70% gas saturation) in Stenlille-17 and 18 are approximately 7 and 9 m thick in zone 3, and 0 and 12 m thick in zone 5, respectively. These gas column thicknesses are in good agreement with the high-probability gas sandstone anomalies. There are also thinner gas columns in zone 1 and 2 that vary between 1–5 m in thickness at various well locations and smaller gas saturations (5–10%) that could trigger the "fizz gas" effect for an uniform fluid mixture at the seismic scale (Fig. 11), where it becomes difficult to seismically distinguish high and low gas saturations (Han and Batzle, 2002). However, the high-probability anomalies seems to primarily resolve the main gas accumulations, particularly within zone 3 and zone 5. The inversion also suggests some lower gas probabilities within the deeper zone 6, although not as strong as the more shallow anomalies. A fault is also apparent by the abrupt time shift in the upper part of the Gassum interval, as illustrated by the black dashed line.

Figure 21 shows the posterior probability map of the gas sandstone LFC, extracted along the Upper target horizon with a +22 ms time shift applied corresponding to zone 3. A high-probability anomaly appears at the structural high and agrees well with the locations of the main injection wells into zones 1–3, namely Stenlille-2, 7, 9 and 11. On the top map, the arbitrary line in Fig. 20 is illustrated by the black dashed line. On the bottom map, an additional black mask is overlaid derived from a structural dip attribute to the plane reflector (Chopra and Marfurt, 2007), implying discontinuities or complex reflections. The dashed white lines show some interpretations of two lineaments crossing through the gas injection area towards the top of the structure, representing faults or possibly some abrupt facies changes. The area of the high-probability anomaly corresponding to the gas injection in zone 3 is estimated to approximately 2.56 km².

Stenlille-4 is an observational safety well placed further south-west at the fringes of the structural high for monitoring possible gas migrations toward the spill-point of the four-way closure. In 1990 and 2013, Stenlille-4 registered higher gas concentrations, and the reservoir management strategy was consequently adjusted to avert further lateral

Fig. 20. Posterior probability section of gas sandstone along an arbitrary line. Water saturation and gamma ray logs from intersecting wells are plotted on top for QC.

Fig. 21. Posterior probability maps of gas sandstone extracted from Upper target with +22 ms shift, corresponding to zone 3, with (a) showing the arbitrary line in Fig. 20 indicated as the black dashed line along with the intersecting wells, and (b) displaying the map corendered with a structural dip attribute seen as a black overlay mask with some interpretations shown by white dashed lines.

gas migration. The distribution map in Fig. 21 reveals that the gas in zone 3 was probably not very far from the Stenlille-4 location at the time of the seismic survey. The most prominent migration routes away from the structural high seems to go in the southwest and northeast directions (pink arrows).

The inversion erroneously predicts high probability anomalies westwards from the gas injection area. This is a consequence of (1) only one input seismic volume is used to constrain the predictions of several possible LFCs, which yields a more ill-posed and ambiguous inverse problem prone to misclassifications, and (2) there might be some lithological changes at the zone 3 interval when moving downflank from the structural high, such as varying types of clay properties, varying porosities or biogenic gases, which tends to mimic the elastic properties of the gas sandstones. Because well data is missing at these specific locations, it is not possible to further investigate what is actually causing these presumed misclassifications.

Figure 22 shows the posterior probability map extracted from the Upper target horizon with a +38 ms shift corresponding to zone 5. This zone is operated as three separate compartments divided by the outlined faults as indicated in the bottom map, as the faults seem to act as fluid flow barriers. The pink arrow also points at some high-probability gas fingering which seems to follow the interpreted NW-SE fault, although the gas has not migrated as far SW towards Stenlille-4 as the gas in zone 3 in Fig. 21. The area of the high-probability anomaly corresponding to the gas injection in zone 5 is estimated to approximately 1 km². Note that the gas anomaly do not conform with the top isocontour of the Upper target horizon corresponding to the reservoir apex. This is likely because the zone 5 gas injection via the anticline limbs started only two years prior to the seismic survey, and the gas plume has therefore not had sufficient time to migrate into the structural trap (Ringrose and Bentley, 2021).

6. Discussions

From a geological viewpoint, the Stenlille aquifer represents a good reservoir analog for the nearby Havnsø structure, approximately 30 km

Fig. 22. Posterior probability maps of gas sandstone extracted from top of zone 5, with (a) showing the injection wells and the net gas injection volumes, and (b) displaying the map corendered with a fault attribute seen as a black overlay mask with some interpretations in white dashed lines.

further northwest (Fig. 1) as a possible CO₂ storage site. The Stenlille gas storage facility is covered with what is regarded as the most comprehensive dataset onshore Denmark, and is certainly the most relevant dataset for seismic characterization of reservoir properties in the Havnsø CO₂ prospect. However, as seismic data is only available in a post-stack rather than a pre-stack format, the seismic distinction between various facies becomes an inverse problem that only relies on the acoustic impedance contrasts between facies of interest. One of the main objectives for this study was to investigate whether mapping the gas distributions at Stenlille was feasible. Fortunately, the injected natural gas at Stenlille yields a considerable acoustic impedance decrease that stands out from the other facies. Moreover, the acoustic properties of the natural gas are much similar as to a CO₂ fluid under the same temperature and pressure conditions, meaning that we could expect similar results if the natural gas was replaced by CO₂. Hence, the Stenlille dataset represents an excellent case study under the conditions of fairly limited and old seismic data, where seismic imaging of the Gassum target is also challenging because the high-velocity chalk package in the overburden absorbs seismic wave energy. Therefore, the results obtained in this study demonstrates that it is feasible to make reasonable gas predictions, even under limited data conditions. This is encouraging because modern seismic data will provide better signal-to-noise ratio and additional pre-stack inversion parameters, such as the V_p/V_s ratio and possibly density, to further constrain the non-uniqueness of the inverse problem (Fig. 9).

When interpreting the posterior probabilities for the gas sandstone LFC, one may suspect that these anomalies are strongly driven by variations in porosity or lithology variations rather than pore fluid content (Fig. 9). However, by evaluating the inversion results with water saturation logs along relevant wells, this suspicion is disapproved. Fig. 23 shows, left-to-right, acoustic impedance, shale volume, porosity and water saturation logs and the posterior probability as a virtual log track along Stenlille-18. Notice that a 70–80% posterior probability for the gas sandstone is predicted at the upper part of zone 5 aligning with the gas column, whereas the probability is close to halved in the deeper water saturated part of zone 5 at similar porosities. This plot illustrates that the posterior probabilities are sufficiently sensitive to acoustic impedance changes as function of varying pore fluid content within the Gassum interval. Thus, for high posterior probabilities approaching 70%, the gas sandstone LFC can be used as a gas indicator. Furthermore, the high-

Fig. 23. Stenlille-18 from left-to-right: acoustic impedance, shale volume, porosity, water saturation and inverted posterior probability for the gas sandstone LFC.

probability distributions in Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 looks more like fluid plumes rather than high-porosity or shaly bodies, which reinforce the confidence in that the inversion captures the injected gas. The rock physics templates in Fig. 11b demonstrate how additional V_p/V_s data could constrain the non-uniqueness of the inverse problem (Johansen et al., 2013) as it is very sensitive to fluid variations relative to AI.

A useful parameter for studying thin layers, such as the gas sandstones at Stenlille, is the posterior-to-prior probability ratio. If we obtain a probability ratio close to 1, the posterior and prior are similar, which indicates that the seismic data do not contain sufficient information to drive the seismic inversion, e.g. due to limited resolution. The estimated probability ratio for the gas anomalies in zone 3 and zone 5 (Fig. 20) indicates that the data is driving the probability up by a factor of 3 or even exceeding 4, even though these represents relatively thin gas layers. The false gas anomalies in Zone 6 (Fig. 20) and downflank from the Stenlille structure in Zone 3 (Fig. 21) shows a lower probability ratio, meaning that they are less supported by the seismic data compared to the more shallow gas anomalies in Zone 3 and Zone 5. Hence, the probability ratio parameter was useful for de-risking some of the false positives, and add confidence to the gas predictions in the reservoir zones utilized for gas storage in the Stenlille aquifer.

It is paramount to interpret the LFC probabilities by questioning some of the limitations and configurations of the inversion. For example, what were the assumptions and simplifications made when defining the LFC definitions? Do the LFCs capture all the facies within the target window, and do they exhibit a unique acoustic impedance distribution? How much is the inverse problem influenced by non-uniqueness considering the number of input data and overlapping elastic properties of the LFCs? Do the inversion results conform with geological structures or match well log observations? Running through some critical questions for the inversion may be helpful to boost confidence in some specific anomalies, discard them or deem them inconclusive under the conditions given by the data and inversion setup.

7. Conclusions

The presented rock physics and pore fluid substitution modeling of the in situ natural gas and CO_2 saturation exhibited a similar seismic

response of the Gassum Formation in the Stenlille aquifer gas storage. This indicates that the seismic data from Stenlille is suitable for predicting the seismic response of the analogous Havnsø prospect for varying CO_2 saturation. Furthermore, a Bayesian post-stack inversion for litho-fluid classification was conducted to outline the injected natural gas distributions based on the available 3D seismic post-stack data from the Stenlille aquifer. The gas injected into the Gassum Formation yields a low acoustic impedance response that separate from the other facies, making it possible to seismically resolve and distinguish the gas. High-probability gas sandstone anomalies were predicted within the two reservoir zones used for gas storage at the time of the seismic survey. The outlined gas distributions are in good agreement with well log observations, gas injection and withdrawal history and conforms with the Stenlille anticline structure and injection points. This study indicate a good potential for seismic characterization and monitoring of future CO_2 storage in geological settings similar to the Stenlille aquifer, such as the Havnsø CO_2 prospect.

Data Availability

Data associated with this research are available and can be obtained by contacting the corresponding author upon a reasonable request.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Kenneth Bredesen: Conceptualization, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None declared.

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Supplementary material

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103583](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103583)

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